

EULAC
MUSEUMS

Select Ecomuseums Bibliography

SELECT ECOMUSEUMS BIBLIOGRAPHY

Ecomuseums, Community-Based Museology, Heritage Management & Sustainable Tourism

This bibliography has been prepared by the Museums, Galleries and Collections Research Institute, School of Art History and Museum & Gallery Studies, University of St Andrews, as part of the EU-LAC Museums research project, funded by the Horizon2020 programme under Grant Agreement number 693669.

It has been edited by Sherill Keefe and Thea Bjoeranger under the guidance of Dr Karen Brown, and has benefitted especially from the very generous contributions of Dr Gerard Corsane, Professor Peter Davis, and Hugues de Varine.

Our bibliography has been arranged according to language and in alphabetical order. It is being shared on our project web portal to reach as many researchers as possible working on our project theme of ecomuseums, community museology, and sustainability relating to heritage.

It is intended to be a working bibliography which can be added to through time as our research deepens and expands beyond geographic and linguistic borders. Areas of uncertain reference details therefore remain highlighted in this document.

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